

INDUSTRIALIZATION AND RTM PROCESS AUTOMATIZATION

Urrutibeazkoa I., Guisasola J.R., Arrazola P.J., Etxabe A.M^a

Composite materials laboratory - Eskola Politeknikoa
C/ Loramendi, 4 - 20500 - MONDRAGON

ABSTRACT

As a result of the growing industrial interest in the RTM process, the laboratory for composite materials of the Eskola Politeknikoa (Polytechnic School), has used this technology to develop one cell for the manufacture of parts, in collaboration with Vetrotex España. The cell consists of an injection area, a preforming machine, and several storage areas.

At the same time, a Computer Aided Production Management program has been developed for personal computers.

The goal of the study has been the optimization of the process, working in the time reduction of its various stages, and facilitating the task of the operator. In addition, a through study is under way on the main variables that take part in this process.

The results obtained in the various simulations will allow a deeper knowledge of the RTM process and, subsequently, a broadening of its industrial use.

KEYWORDS

COMPOSITES, RTM, INJECTION, PREFORMING, OPTIMIZATION, MANUFACTURING, CAPM

1. INTRODUCTION

The R.T.M. (Resin Transfer Moulding) process is a method of transforming composite materials which consists of injecting an accelerated catalyzed resin into a closed mould where a reinforcement (1) has previously been placed.

The dry reinforcement is inserted into the mould before it is closed, with the aim, on the one hand, of making it easier to place and, on the other hand, of guaranteeing a greater homogeneity in the distribution of the fibre in the parts, and thus making it possible to consider the carrying out of pre-shaping or preforming.

The interest in this method, as opposed to manual processes (contact moulding, simultaneous projection), resides in the fact that it allows parts to be obtained with the two sides well finished, eliminates the incidence of labour, reduces the finishing operations, increases the production per mould and decreases to a great extent the high percentage of styrene emissions. (2)

There is, however, the inconvenience that the investment in machinery and moulds is higher and, therefore, this method is considered suitable for production runs of 5,000 parts (3).

If it is required to make the method more profitable or even valid for greater production runs, it is necessary to consider a higher degree of automation of the process, so that the amount of intervention by the operators in the handling of moulds, placing the reinforcement, adjusting the parameters, etc. is lower.

Because of this, the **Eskola Politeknikoa**, which has been working on its studies of composite materials for the last 6 years, has developed a manufacturing cell for parts by means of the R.T.M. process, composed of an injection cell and a preforming installation, backed up by a computer system which helps in the tasks of managing the cell.

The aim of the project is to demonstrate the possibilities offered by the R.T.M. process to small and medium-sized companies that are currently working with manual processes.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE R.T.M. CELL

The specifications established for the cell were as follows:

- ▶ The number of operators working on the cell will be one.
- ▶ The cell must allow parts to be manufactured with two moulds at the same time.

Fig. 1: R.T.M. Cell developed at the Eskola Politeknikoa.

- ▶ The number of different parts will be 5, with the possibility of having two moulds for each part.
- ▶ It must be possible to work with two types of resin, even though this would mean the use of an injection machine for each type of resin.
- ▶ The possibility of working with several types of gel-coat, even up to 5, one for each part.
- ▶ The moulds must hold to a certain unification:
 - Maximum dimensions: 1000 mm x 500 cm x 500 mm.
 - The upper part of the mould must have a fixed pulley at each end of its width.
 - Both parts of the mould must have flat support surfaces.

Starting from the above-mentioned specifications and the diagram of the R.T.M. process (Figure 2), the cell illustrated in the diagram in Figure 3 has been developed.

In the diagram, two parts can be distinguished:

- a) The injection cell itself.
- b) The preforming installation.

2.1. Injection cell

Inside the injection cell, the following positions or areas can be distinguished:

- ▶ Mould closing and opening position.
- ▶ Gel-coat application position.
- ▶ Injection position.
- ▶ Transport system between the different positions.
- ▶ Mould store.
- ▶ Raw materials store: preforms, inserts, etc.

2.1.1. Mould closing and opening position

In this position, the closing and opening of the mould is carried out (1).

Fig. 2: Diagram of the R.T.M. process.

A machine which was designed and built in the Eskola is available and allows:

- ▶ A closing force to be applied.
- ▶ A demoulding (withdrawal) force to be applied.
- ▶ The upper part of the mould to be turned.

A series of belts allow the demoulding and the turning of the upper part of the mould by means of fixed pulleys situated on the said upper part.

The table has a series of concealable (retracting) rollers, which make it easier to insert the mould into the machine and which retract when the closing force is applied.

The main features of the machine are:

- Maximum closing (locking) force: 15,000 kp.
- Maximum speed of the upper slide: 2 m/min.
- Turning speed of the mould: 7 r.p.m.
- Height of the table: 1,100 mm.
- Slide stroke: 650 mm.
- Maximum dimensions of the mould: 1,000 x 500 x 500
- Minimum dimensions of the mould: 400 x 300 x 300

Fig. 4: Diagram of the preforming installation.

In the design of this module, the possibility that the layers of mat might be supplied after having been previously cut has also been taken into account.

The module allows the width to be adapted to different dimensions according to the mat which it is wished to use.

The process also achieves a system whereby, while the press moulds the part and the operator dislodges or removes it, other layers of mat are already being heated and prepared to be preformed.

► Module 3: Store

The function of this module is to supply the feeder module with a certain number of layers of mat.

It consists of a metallic structure with a capacity for 5 rolls or reels of mat. Taking the layers of mat which are required, they are placed between two powered rollers and supplied to the feeder module at the moment it requires them.

The main features of the machine are:

- Frequency rate 20 strokes/minute.
- Height = 3 m.
- Maximum pressing force = 15 Tn.
- Maximum slide down speed = 50 cm/sec.
- Mould dimensions : 500 * 500 mm.
- Slide stroke = 500 mm.
- Maximum heating surface = 700 mm.
* 600 mm.

- Oven power = 9 Kw.
- Number of rolls in the store = 5
- Maximum surface mass = 3,000 gr/m².
- Centralized control.
- Space occupied: 6 x 1.1 x 3 m.

2.3. Method of working with 1 operator and two moulds

Each time that one wishes to start the manufacture of a part, the mould for this part must be inserted into the injection cell from the mould store. To do this, and with the help of a trolley, the operator will take the mould and place it at the injection position.

For both insertion and extraction, the moulds must be kept closed to prevent them from becoming damaged or dirty.

The mould, once in the cell, is slid over the rollers by the operator to the machine to assist with closing. Once there, with the help of the machine, the upper part of the mould is lifted in order to be able to turn it. Before turning the upper part and then resting it on the table, the lower part is extracted from the machine and moved towards the injection position.

When the mould and counter-mould are on the roller track, the operator pushes both of them towards the gel-coat application position.

After the operator has applied gel-coat by means of a

pistol, there is a wait to allow partial polymerization to take place.

After this, the operator slides both the mould and the counter-mould towards the closure assistance machine.

Once that the upper part is placed in the closure assistance machine, the operator proceeds to turn it in order to prepare it for insertion into the lower part.

While the lower part of the mould is at the closure assistance table, the already preformed or trimmed reinforcement is inserted. The operator, once that the upper part has descended, moves back the retractable rollers until they become concealed. Always with the help of the machine, strong pressure is applied onto the upper part of the mould, in order to proceed with closing it by means of the fast-locking bolts.

When the mould is closed, the upper slide of the machine is raised and the mould is extracted in order to move it to the injection position. To do this, the retractable rollers will again have been raised.

Once in the injection position, and after the injection has been carried out, it is necessary to wait for the polymerization of the resin.

When polymerization has finished, the mould is taken to the closure assistance machine so that the part can be extracted. Pressing with the upper table on the mould, the fast-locking bolts are loosened and the upper part of the mould is raised by means of the pulleys. The lower part of the mould is then extracted from the machine and demoulding of the part can take place by means of air, wedges, etc...

The upper part of the mould is made to turn and descend onto the table.

After cleaning and applying a demoulding substance, if it is considered necessary, the mould is ready to manufacture another part.

The following parts are thus successively produced.

By analyzing what has been said so far, and with the aim of obtaining greater productivity, it has been considered that the most logical arrangement would be to have one operator with two moulds. This allows the operator to be occupied with the second mould while the gel-coat and resin in the first are in polymerization, and vice-versa.

The increase in productivity by following this arrangement could be 30%.

Because of this, duplicated roller spaces have been placed in the injection cell in case of a possible coincidence of operations: injection position and gel-coat application position.

On the other hand, it is considered that with an appropriate study and by performing certain modifications in the cell, it would be possible to think about the possibility of working with two operators and three moulds or even with 3 operators and 4 moulds.

Fig. 5: Method of working with one operator and two moulds.

Operation	Duration
1- Application of demoulder	5'
2- Application of gel-coat	5'
3- Curing (cross-linking) of gel-coat	10'
4- Fitting of reinforcements	10'
5- Closing of mould and counter-mould	5'
6- Injection of resin	5'
7- Cross-linking of resin	20'
8- Opening of part	5'
9- Demoulding of part	5'
10- Prefinishing of part	5'

Fig. 6: Operations in the R.T.M. process.

2.4. G.P.A.O. Programme

The aim of this programme is to administer the purchasing, manufacturing and sales functions of the cell, or, in the case of a company, of the cell and another series of centres.

The G.P.A.O. programme developed in this project is an M.R.P. which, apart from fulfilling the conditions implicit in these kind of packages, carries out the optimization of the production for those centres called bottlenecks in the R.T.M. process, which usually prove to be the injection cells. (6)

The model of administration or management which has been adopted is a mixed M.R.P. and T.O.C. system. It is called a mixed system because the calculation mechanics of the M.R.P. are used, supported on the concepts of the T.O.C. (Figure 7). This is:

- ▶ Optimization of the manufacturing of the injection cell or any other bottleneck centre, by taking into account the change times and programming it in such a way that the manufacturing time at this centre is minimised.
- ▶ Using the M.R.P. to see the manufacturing necessities of the resource defined as a bottleneck (injection cell), as well as of all the other manufactured or purchased products.

The programme is run on a compatible PC 386 personal computer with mathematical coprocessor.

Fig. 7: Algorithm of the G.P.A.O. programme.

2.8.1. Structure of the programme

The programme is divided into four modules (options of the main menu):

- a) Technical database.
- b) Order management.
- c) Planning of material requirements.
- d) Methods and Budgeting.

a) Technical database

Maintains and manages the data concerning items, lists of material, work centres, routes, stores and production timetables; thus allowing updating (adding, modifying, erasing), as well as providing access to the data either by screen or by printer.

b) Order management

Carries out the control and monitoring of purchasing, manufacturing and sales. This means that it maintains

and manages data about suppliers, customers, sources of supply, purchase orders, work orders, stock situations, reception of orders, cost control of orders, materials returned, etc.

c) Planning of material requirements

Calculates the requirements of material starting from an ordering programme, suggesting manufacturing and purchase orders, as well as the optimum manufacturing programmes for the centre or centres defined as bottlenecks (R.T.M. injection cells).

d) Methods and Budgeting

Obtains joint ways of working for the R.T.M. injection cells, starting from the manufacturing and curing times for each part, and calculates sales budgets for the new products that enter into the order book.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be established:

- ▶ The cell which has been developed can be used in small companies exactly as it stands at present or with certain modifications. Thus, although at present it has been designed to work with 1 operator and 2 moulds, it could be adapted to work with 2 or 3 operators and 4 or more moulds with a view to obtaining a higher production rate.
- ▶ The G.P.A.O. programme which has been developed is suitable for a medium-sized company which applies another process apart from the R.T.M. process. The fact that it is performed on personal computers and its ease of use make it more attractive than other programmes available on the market at present.

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